

PARACHOR OF POTASSIUM DICHROMATE AND CONSTITUTION OF CHROMIC ACID

BY W. V. BHAGWAT, V. A. MOGHE AND P. M. TOSHNIWAL

The parachor of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in aqueous solution has been determined. The results when compared with parachors of K_2CrO_4 and CrO_3 confirm the view that CrO_3 exists in solution mainly as $H_2Cr_2O_7$, dichromic acid.

Parachor of potassium dichromate has been determined by Sugden and Wilkins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 263) by fusion method and the value obtained is 450.8. Lakhani and Daroga (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 41) got the value 450.6 by solution method, using $P_{H_2O} = 54$ and applying their formula

$$P_m = (1+x)P_p + x \frac{P_x}{2}$$

We have shown (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 226) that there is no justification for this formulae and that the correct value to be substituted for P_{H_2O} is 52.3. Introducing this correction and using the usual formula

$$P_m = (1-x)P_p + xP_x$$

the value comes out to be 414 by Lakhani and Daroga's result.

We have therefore investigated the parachor of potassium dichromate at various concentrations and our results are as follows.

x .	M_m .	Temp.	D .	γ .	P_m .	P_x .	x .	M_m .	Temp.	D .	γ .	P_m .	P_x .
0.007169	19.96	20°	1.074	76.26	54.92	447.7	0.003794	19.095	30°	1.037	72.85	53.74	484.9
		30°	1.071	74.06	54.68	414.2			40°	1.033	71.32	53.73	484.7
		50°	1.061	70.96	54.59	401.7			50°	1.029	70.21	53.69	471.7
0.005718	19.57	22°	1.059	74.42	54.27	439.9	0.00300	18.83	20°	1.031	71.71	53.16	440.0
		30°	1.056	73.10	54.17	414.5			30°	1.026	71.06	53.22	460.0
		40°	1.052	71.85	54.19	417.9			40°	1.020	69.68	53.26	468.0
		50°	1.048	70.65	54.18	416.1			50°	1.015	68.22	53.28	472.0
0.004283	19.18	22°	1.043	75.67	53.91	476.3							
		40°	1.038	72.78	53.99	494.9							
		50°	1.032	71.37	54.03	504.8							

The value of parachor as calculated from atomic parachor ($K=110$, $Cr=54$, $O=20$) is $P_{K_2Cr_2O_7} = 468$. If, however, we represent the constitution of potassium dichromate by the formula

then we have two polar linkages and four semi-polar bonds each of which has a value = -1.6. Hence $P_{K_2Cr_2O_7} = 468 - 9.6 = 458.4$. The experimental values as obtained by us are near about these values although they vary with the concentration of potassium dichromate.

The structural formula for chromium trioxide, potassium chromate and potassium dichromate according to electronic theory of valency are

The corresponding values of observed and calculated parachor for them are :

	Calc.	Obs. in solution
CrO ₃	134	102
K ₂ CrO ₄	347.6	195
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	458.4	440

The lower values indicate some sort of ionisation. If CrO₃ exists in solution as H₂CrO₄ its constitution will be represented in a similar manner as K₂CrO₄ and hence it should be possible to obtain the value of CrO₃ group in solution from the values of parachor of K₂CrO₄. Unfortunately the value of $2P_K$ is alone 220 and hence it is impossible to obtain the value of CrO₃ group from $P_{K_2CrO_4}$ by the procedure

$$P_{CrO_3} = P_{K_2CrO_4} - 2P_K - P_O.$$

Even if we assume that ionic parachor of potassium is not the same as its atomic parachor, yet the results with K₂Cr₂O₇ in which K ions are also present, shows that it should not be very different as the calculated and observed parachors of K₂Cr₂O₇ are nearly the same. On the other hand from $P_{K_2Cr_2O_7}$ we get

$$2P_{CrO_3} = P_{K_2Cr_2O_7} - 2P_K - P_O = 440 - 220 - 20 = 200, \quad \text{or, } P_{CrO_3} \text{ in solution} = \frac{200}{2} = 100.$$

This value nearly equals the observed value 102 in solution. The parachor observations therefore support the view that chromic acid exists in solution mainly as H₂Cr₂O₇ and equilibrium exists of the type $H_2Cr_2O_7 + H_2O \rightleftharpoons 2H_2CrO_4$.

Bhagwat and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 913; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 2405) have determined the absorption of K₂CrO₄, K₂Cr₂O₇ and CrO₃ solutions, in water. Their results confirm the view that in concentrated solution CrO₃ exists mainly as H₂Cr₂O₇.

We have determined the conductivity of chromium tri oxide solution and calculated the values for μ_∞ from observed results assuming that CrO₃ exists in solution as H₂Cr₂O₇ and H₂CrO₄. We have then determined the values for μ_∞ for K₂CrO₄ and K₂Cr₂O₇ solutions experimentally. From these values, we calculated the values for μ_∞ H₂CrO₄ and μ_∞ H₂Cr₂O₇ by applying Kohlrausch law. The actual values are not very correct but they are correct enough to show that the calculated value agrees with the observed value of CrO₃ determined as H₂Cr₂O₇. In short the observations support the view that CrO₃ exists in solution mainly as H₂Cr₂O₇.

We have tried to determine coagulating power of CrO₃ assuming it to exist as H₂Cr₂O₇ and H₂CrO₄ and have compared it with the coagulating power of K₂CrO₄ and K₂Cr₂O₇, using Fe(OH)₃ sol. The results do not help to draw any conclusion.

The observations of Bewen and Chatwin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2081) on photochemical oxidation of alcohol by potassium chromate using dilute solution support the existence of HCrO₄ ions in dilute solutions.

The results of Koppel and Blumenthal (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, 53, 228) on boiling points of aqueous solutions of Cr(O)₃ and of Sherril (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 1641), Kremann (*Wein Akad. Ber.*, 1911, 120, ii, b, 339), Buchner and Prins (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 81, 113) on freezing point, however support the view that CrO₃ exists mainly as H₂CrO₄.